

SPORTS ARE GYMNASTICS IN ACTION SERIES-BE THE
MANIFESTATION OF COME.

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***Anatatsiya:** Man smart, mobility toe'lish in gymnastics importance is larger. Gymnastic exercises of various toe'become, sports type all this from exercise to use. They gavin muscles the development of help - giving, to 'g'ri the body shape. This is the reason for also o'educational institutions, treatment-preventive work in and work out in the field, military service are widely applied.*

Key words: Sports gimnatika, to rely on, sit on them, Cho'qytirish, stand, Throw, jumping, running, osilish.

Gymnastics workout more a significant side is, this exercise of the body and all the members equally positive effects ko'rsat is. Physical education lessons in your life o'ta necessary , which is running, walking, rope tirmashib out, from the fence increased transition, balance to maintain, jump developments to fulfill - related skills and qualifications harvest we will.

"Gymnastics" the concept of broad sense, when you realize, her sport gymnastics, artistic gymnastics, rhythm found, acrobat gymnastics like types there are.

This toe'in education you of gymnastics a few exercises with acquainted, sports equipment most common in the acrobat of exercise and physical qualities that develops particular exercise to do (on the rope jump, press chambarak of the exercise you complete, hands whom doing so finds bend-write, to draw, umbaloq increased, in kuraklar erect stand and etc.) you will learn.

Gymnastics terms or terms of results, separate or complex action, the state of the environment a short example naming is understood. Terms o'be qitish and the reader, between the circulation-in the relationship of excessive description escape the opportunity to gives and just the action of exercise most characteristic features of the show with is limited. Gymnastics terminology convenience, accuracy and short ministry with a difference it makes. Terms to remember which remains toe'lish the goal is.

Below, gymnastic exercises and their terminology with you will get acquainted. O'educational and independent sessions frequently occurring action and occurrence of terms to remember can keep you stay.

Review stand (10-picture): a) the main stand; b) your legs yelka width open stand; d) o'ng (left) leg forward a step away without stand; e) foot chalishtirib stand; f) the right (left) knee to stand; g) kurakda stand; h) boshda stand; i) at the hand of the stand.

the members sit — floor or gymnastics outfit to sit on the condition (11-picture): a) sit b) your legs yelka width open sit; d) rectangular sit; e) your legs on top of up to sit;

f) top ko'comb your legs and hold (embrace) sit;

g) o'ng (left) to the heel sit; h) your legs yelka kengligidaochib, qo'shpoya on sit; i) the number of sit.

a) to cho'qqayib; b) yarimcho'qqayish; do'ngsimon yarimcho'qqayish; e) back down yarimcho'qqayish; f) forward bending yarimcho'qqayish; g) the right (left) leg yarimcho'qqayish.

Review on: a)cho'qqayib to rely on; b)the right knee on, left leg to lift up; d)thehands on, in the full bent, to; e) to wrists on to lay; f) the back of the hands to rely on;

g)hand finds doing so whom on hold on (qo'shpoyada); h)qo'shpoyada hand finds doing so whom tirsakdan bend to rely on; i) qo'shpoyada whom hand finds doing so forward-to'g'riga transmission to rely on; j)qo'shpoyada your legs up lift, hands and kurakda to rely on; k) qo'shpoyada rectangular to rely on; l) qo'shpoya on your legs wide open, to rely on; m) right or the left foot cho'qqayib to rely on; n) finds the hand of whom doing so tirsakdan buk meat without belly with lay on, left foot back up to; o)your legs wide open , without bend down, hands to rely on. g

the cast members — right (left) the feet of any side is thrown, above the knee to

bend will try or that after the yield is the condition (14-picture): a) to remove; b) when you remove it, side to side to bend down; d) the right to remove, forward bending; e) the right (left) side to the deep throw; f) the left foot with the right to the thrown.

Hands movement and the condition (15- picture): a) on erect standing without the hands on the bottom; b) the hands on the side of the side in the bottom; d) hands side to side for me; e)hands side to side above;

f)thehands above; g) hands - chip, tirsakdan bruised; h) hands yelka at the top, tirsakdan bruised.

The legs of the movement and the condition a) to the left (right) foot slightly forward to carry; b) forward-down; d) forward-to'g'riga; e) forward-up; f) slightly back up to; g) to back-down;

h) back-tog'ri to; i) right (left) leg to the knee slightly to bend; j) the left (right) leg forward and stretched, the knee to

bend; k) the left (right) to the feet, back, bring, the knee to bend; l) the left (right) leg side to side get, the knee to bend.

Review of down — gavin sag (17-picture): a) to‘liq down; b) yarimengashish; d) forward slightly to bend down; e) before-

ha-down to bend down; f) back down, a methodology‘lni to the ground extension; g) your legs wide open, forward-to‘g‘riga down; h) full bending, your legs quchoqlashib.

Balance to maintain — going a foot in or on stand horizontal condition (18-picture): a) the right leg balance, to keep; b) engashgan without balance to maintain; d) a foot from side to side up the balance to keep; e) back down the balance to maintain; f) the left (right) foot chip transmission is a balance to maintain; g) chip transmitted the foot I have to hold it in case the balance to maintain; h) a feet above, the focused mode and the balance to keep.

Arg‘amchi with exercise (19-picture): a) sirtmoq a jump; b) your legs forward and stretched jump; d) the foot of the crop jump.

Osilish of sports equipment shug‘ullana action and condition (20-picture): a) osilish; b) hanging without sprains; d) the foot above the head, to the bottom on the stand are osilish;

e) rectangular osilish of; f) cho‘qqayib osilish; g) hanging without sprains; h) lying without osilish; i) yelka , along with in turnik hang stand; j) the knee bruised limbs osilish.

Up the work — hanging to stand out to rely and lower lean more high to rely on the transition (21-picture): a) power with up to; b) rose, after to become; d) do not bend and, after the pick up; e) at the back, abdomen, boosting on carry out work; f) forward shaken up; g) the right (left) leg ahead to rise.

Akrobatika exercises (22-picture): a) jump umbaloq increased; b) the right knee on, back umbaloq increased; d) salto (shaken);

e) ko‘we have pride; f) the focused and yarimshpagat.

Gymnastics bacillus with the main cases (23-picture):

a) stick to the bottom; b) stick ko'krak in; d) the stick above; e) the stick yelkada; f) stick your head in the right side; g) the hand on the right side-for me, stick a tip above; h) stick yelkada, the right tip above.

Gymnastics workout **written forms**, there are: fine, atamaviy, chizmali (24-picture). This with along, fine-chizmali form also is there, it is to exercise writing them in describe with methodology'shib get go.

Gymnastics types of

Human in various actions to perform to the ability is there. This is the reason for also gymnastics exercises in variety and in this exercise type is allocated.

Basic gymnastics — gymnastics relatively independent type toe'become, different ages of people in general physical developed, supported the development and health strengthening for physical education is used.

Lessonin ulot to saflan, umumrivojlantiruvchi and practical exercises, various review jump, gymnastics equipment workout, artistic gymnastics simple elements and akrobatika of exercise is made. The body's work 's ability to increase, to'g'ri qadqomatni in the formation of the main gymnastics great importance it has. Lessonulot of the exact order, strictly discipline and of music accompaniment from the get go.

Women's gymnastics basic gymnastics of the types of one toe'become, in which the female body properties into account are taken.

Women's gymnastics elasticity, tortiluvchanlikni development, movement aesthetic represent, rhythm and temp feel to make of the qualifications possessed, it is the body, walking, improving, improving. Lessonthe ulot, usually, of music, the accompaniment is held. Them per week 2-3 times o' - check-in passengers to target it.

Athletic gymnastics power to the development of mo'ljallab the physical exercise system is, of the male external appearance, and each party to the physical preparation of the formation is directed.

Professional-practice gymnastics in physical education of the structural part of the toe'become, involved general physical development, their action and the ability to improve, chosen their profession successfully to take directed.

O'central secondary school physical education on educational work in the process the children in every way - physical training for **military-practical from gymnastics** are used.

Sports-practical gymnastics every one sports of the type of general and special physical preparation part of it issports results, the o'of sish accelerate the opportunity to gives. Therefore, gymnastics this type of complex action with associated that are not

sports in the type of (into the water jump, fight , and so on), akrobatika exercise is widely applied.

Hygienic gymnastics men physical nurturing and healthylomlashtirishning popular tool is, them with different in a group, in school lessons beginning before you engage in can. Lessonthe ulot not only in the morning, but in the daytime (feeding when it is1.5 — 2 hours later after after) and in the evening sleep from 1 — 2 hours before the transfer , you can. School day in order hygienic gymnastics from o'readers back training-work abilities increase, fatigue start, various diseases prevention to obtain are used.

Mass sports gymnastics type, in particular, sport gymnastics, rhythmic gymnastics and sports of akrobatika consists. They are independent sports types as formed and is developing. This type of the particular start'constipation elements secondary schools physical education program included. Them using "Alpomish" and "Barchinoy" special test some private functions the solution is. Athletes training and sports competitions o'- check-in passengers in the practice of exercise two klassifikatsion program is applied. "B" classification methods on athletes the mass competitions for preparing see. This program "A" classification of the institution is a relatively lightweight and range complex exercise are prepared athletes who for, in the country and international arenada large - scale competitions of conduct for included.

Sports gymnastics men and women exercise, ko'pkurash type consists. Men ko'pkurashi content free exercises, field exercises, rings, qo'shpoya and in turnik exercises includes. Women ko'pkurashiga while free exercise, on review, jump, yakkacho'pda and each different in height qo'shpoya exercises includes.

Artistic gymnastics every different sport facilities with or without them fulfilled the large amount of diverse exercise o'z into gets.

Sports akrobatika of diverse workout to rich: acrobat jump, the pair exercises, ", three-evident" (women) and "in to'rtlik" (men) exercise, as well as, mixed couples for exercises consists.

Item hygienic gymnastics is an rhythm - action with together fulfilled hygienic gymnastics group up makes. Them healthylomlashtirish purpose, general conditions and training conduct rules for combining is. Therefore, all the exercises shug'ullana age and preparations are likely coming, them, for comfortable to be should. Exercise is to the body, any sided effects ko'rsat be, gavin joints and the body's muscles to action bring should. Action of a variety of either'in nalish be completed must: variable speed and each is different in character from the voltage with (fast, slow, strain and to bo'shasha with , and h. k.). This with along, all in the same breath rise to take (ko'krak, a diaphragm, mixed) adopters attention, focus and breath long hold on stand to learn a must.

Human sleeping in not only the muscles, but, most of all, first, nervous 'toqima the rest takes. They feed ingredients and oxygen to toe'present the need is reduced. The heart of the activity and its capacity to decrease, breath out is reduced. Muscle tonusi regulatory toe'ladi, inter-tissue fluid exchange slows down. The man from sleep, stood, slowly the trigger toe'la started in and work the ability to restore. Special respectively the physical lesson the ulot — item hygenic badantarbiya work to relatively quickly will restore the effect is, to the body necessary physical downloads gives you.

How can I item, hygenic badantarbiya the regular lesson ulot to convert the can? Most first of all, it 's enough long period of planning, the need, for example, a year. Every month workout set , replace the stand and each one exercise to the amount of 1 — 2 up boosts go should. Exercise performance during a breath to take speed into account is taken.

Item hygenic badantarbiya of some exercise , the athletes a little light ko'rinib of, previously , such badantarbiya with to deal while complicated seem to be. So to each of a sportsman lesson to ulot itself to fix to be entered, even if the whole set themselves re - made as they can. Thus, hygenic aspects o'zini I am justified exercises of the following from the series are used:

1. Item hygenic badantarbiya the body's tetiklikholatiga quickly o'teeth on the effects that shows workout with start should (a deep breath, take, walk, draw, relaxed running).

2. So'ng hand muscles for exercise use (doing so hand finds to whom write and to bend, each in different directions decisive action, bruised or right hands with circles). This exercise toe'g'i those that had the mobility of the increase in the effects of shows.

3. That then while the foot for exercises bajarishtavsiya is (the knee to bend and to write, shake the bottle featured, yarimoy'reurrection, sitting members of each identical to shake the bottle, depsi nib review).

4. Next place gavin and lumbar muscles for mashqlar bajariladi (forward and back, side to side bent to the work, turn the work, the head and gavin with o'ng and to the left of the rotary action). This group exercise o'the voters back to the very important, because the lesson is in the process of a long time in parta sit straight it will come. This while the muscles loosening, and og'riq appear to take cause you can.

Gymnastics equipment workout

Turnik, methodology'shpoya (brus), yakkacho'p (brevno), "mining" in the world the exercise is complete, the rope tirmashib out, on the jump and chambarak with and in-flight exercises to complete going great strength, skill, agile requirements makes.

The rope tirmashib out

The rope tirmashib out 2 method there are:

1. *Three action with tirmashib out.* Methodology 'arms on the top of the lift, the rope tightly to hold. "A" when you say, to the rope hanging, leg knee bend, the chest towards is pulled and the foot chalishtiriladi. "Two" when I say so, whom finds so doing hand bend, the foot with the rope hard pinch is taken. "Three" when I say, the foot with the rope pinch of taking without hands with the rope in the series to hold, the top and pull harakatlaniladi.

2. *Two in action tirmashib out.* "A" when you say, your legs straighten, rope hands with hold, the series up tirmashib out. "Two" when you say, again, your legs pull, the rope tightly squeeze will hold. Exercise the same way continue will further.

Remember to stay: the rope knee not, just the legs, paws-of the heel with a hard pinch to hold should be. The rope from the down fall is also the methodology 'l and the foot of times it is used in. Slip fall , you can 't.

Turnik in to pull. O'g'i at children high turnik in doing so whom hand finds the top hold, your legs to the ground tekkizmay they will hang, after will be pulled. Daxa that from turnik be increased should. Children intact the exercise you carry out could not, earlier low in turnik to chalqancha hanging without, your legs to the ground and the base I pulled, workout to should be.

Individual 'pda exercise complete

Girls alone 'pdas have a few of exercise take to improve the performance of the can. Walking, turning, one and two feet o'reurrection-stand, one leg stand "First" exercise performance and so on (25rasm). This workout o'g'i at the kids too, they can.

Acrobat exercise

Forward umbaloq increased. Do this to the methodology 'arms on the bed put, the base formed is, the foot with by pushing, forward umbaloq out, then again the initial condition returns (26rasm).

Two time series forward umbaloq increased. Thus, one time ahead of umbaloq increased, the initial condition back after so'ng, again cho'qqayib sit, a time second time umbaloq increase.

In kuraklar erect stand. This exercise gavin muscle development influence ko'rsat is. The exercise o'at g'i children also, the girls also gradually with they can.

This exercise is complete to earlier chalqancha to lay, so'ng your legs, a flat top is up to you need. Methodology'arms using of gavin lower part is raised and the foot standing to the condition is brought.

Back umbaloq increased, in kuraklar erect stand. Do this to cho'qqaygan without whom hand finds doing so the floor before put, g'ujanak is sitting. So'ngra feet from threshold uzmay, rolled on to kuraklar are. Then the methodology of'the arms quickly wrists from bend, starting position is to come, please plaques and tirab, the pelvis without fall, gavin erect is to hold (27-picture). Exercise do beside standing partner in its belidan, one of the legs of the hold, an upright position to stand ko'of maklashish can be.

your legs bend, methodology'arms using boshda erect stand. This exercise is complete to ago cho'qqayib is sit, then hand their plaques yelka width opened, oldinroqda the floor, on also kaft before the floor is put in, as if the triangle formed is. Feet with pushing, them buk meat without a few more seconds hold on are. So'ng initial condition returns. Exercise do beside standing partner to her feet,'i and belidan to hold stand up to help, it can.

Back umbaloq increased, half'I am zilg in case (yarimshpagat) sit. This exercise girls for mo'was ljallab if, earlier back umbaloq out, and then one knee on standing will be. So'ng gavin and correct, back a leg stretched and yarimshpagat position is sitting.

Chalqancha that lies in the situation of "ko'pride we have" the position of the switch. Chalqancha lying without methodology'arms, the top (head towards) is stretched, the foot yelka width will open. "A" when you say of the leg, the knee bend, the heel bed on, hands whom finds doing so tirsakdan bendthe head back will be returned. "Two" when they say hands finds doing so whom is correct, gavin rises and beldan qayishsimon leans. This is the case for 2 — 3 seconds are , and initial condition returns. "Ko'pride" of exercise of the body, the abdomen, waist, arm and leg muscles well you will develop.

Short distance running came, gimnastik " mine" over sideways (transverse) jump (girls for). This exercise is complete to ko'prikchadan bold jump, hands "mine" on , on put, yonboshladi the case to gavin up, the foot yonboshladi the side is turned. The legs, the ends of "mine" over pass with the right hand side to the side lifting or body attached, then "mine"to back , I jump, fall should (28- picture).

On jump. Do this to ago two oyoqlab to jump, ko'prikchaga depsinib out, two oyoqlab to fall mastered to get you need. Jump to fulfilling the following performed are: closer - from a distance running came ko'pride on both feet out and hand finds

doing so whom to'g'riga stretched, sports equipment ("kozyol") on the base form to, hand and foot with pushing without whom hands finds doing so top up, yelka part until you get out. Jump to the exercise fulfillment for security measures ko'rilgandagina permission is given.

Yonboshladi the case of 90° c to turned the jump. "Mine" over and turned jumped in, before the right hand with pushing out (right side to jump to), into the ground in fall other fees will rely on. This workout o'g'i at the kids too, they can.

"Kozyol" over your legs record jump (girls and boys kids for). This exercise is complete to the ago for short distance running came in, ko'prikchadan both feet with depsinib, "kozyol" on hands it is put, and it's pushing out, both feet two, chip is write, the waist slightly to bend down, head up. To the ground, falling before the foot using juftli, slightly buking was. Exercise carrying out before the following, namely standing from a place depsinib the top of the jump, your legs writing, re - juftlash to, methodology'arms base to lying position suddenly jump stand and your legs bend-writing, uzunlikka, pit, high sakrayotganda your legs bend-writing tutorial to get you should.

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